

MSCS-Unet A Melanoma Segmentation Network Based on Multi-Scale Feature Fusion

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Abstract: The most deadly skin disease is melanoma. The disease worsens quickly and is incurable in its advanced stages, so it should be detected and treated early. The main clinical diagnostic basis for the development of this disease is changes in the melanoma focus area. However, my country's current per capita medical resources are tight, resulting in dermatologists' work pressure being very high, and patients' health also facing some challenges. The use of deep learning-based technology for auxiliary diagnosis and treatment can alleviate this contradiction to a certain extent.

In the problem of melanoma segmentation, U-Net network and its many variants based on U-shaped structure are now the mainstream solutions. The U-shaped structure can be divided into three major modules: encoder, decoder, and connection part. For the problem of melanoma segmentation, some special requirements are put forward for these three modules: (1) Since the size of the melanoma lesion area is different, First, there are many cases of lesion occlusion in the data set, so the segmentation model is required to adapt to the variability of lesions in the encoder stage, capture the local features of different areas, and distinguish the lesions from the background to improve the accuracy of segmentation (2) Due to clinical Due to the particularity of the application, it is more necessary to reduce the information loss caused by upsampling in the decoder stage (3) In order to better integrate the lower levels containing more local and detailed information and the higher levels in the decoder containing more For global and semantic information, the connection part should not be limited to the encoder and decoder of the same layer.

Based on the above reasons, this paper designs the melanoma segmentation model MSCS-Unet based on the principle of increasing information fusion and reducing information loss, using a variety of feature fusion technologies, multi-scale feature extraction technologies, and attention mechanisms. On the ISIC2016 and ISIC2017 data sets, the accuracy of MSCS-Unet is 2.01% and 1.55% ahead of U-Net. The model has achieved an excellent balance between lightweight and efficient and accurate segmentation, and can assist experienced medical personnel. Reduce the burden of identifying disease areas. And using U-Net as Baseline, ablation experiments were conducted on the ISIC2016 and ISIC2017 data sets for the three proposed modules. Using the modules proposed in this article alone, the segmentation results are better than Baseline, proving the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Keywords: Melanoma; Deep Learning; Image Segmentation

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Introduction

Melanoma is a malignant tumor with the characteristics of rapid deterioration and easy metastasis. The basic principle of early detection and early treatment should be adhered to in clinical diagnosis and treatment. Therefore, accurate segmentation of early lesion areas is crucial. In recent years, with the rapid development of deep learning technology, melanoma segmentation using deep learning has become an important means of auxiliary diagnosis and treatment^[1].

Deep learning is a machine learning method based on artificial neural networks. Deep neural networks trained through large-scale data can learn complex features and patterns from images and achieve automatic segmentation of melanoma lesions^[2]. This method can not only improve the accuracy and efficiency of segmentation, but also help doctors formulate treatment plans and evaluate prognosis more quickly.

Segmentation models based on U-shaped structures have always occupied an important position in the field of medical image segmentation^[3]. This type of model adopts a symmetric encoder-decoder structure, so that the feature map can be processed layer by layer symmetrically during the encoding and decoding process. In the encoder stage, local features of the image and higher-level semantic information are obtained layer by layer, and the feature maps between the encoder and the decoder are connected through skip connections, so that the decoder can obtain multi-scale feature information from different levels. Moreover, the number of U-shaped parameters is usually relatively small, which ensures the training and inference efficiency of the model. The above characteristics make the application of U-shaped structure in the field of medical image segmentation more convenient and practical. Therefore, for the specific application scenario of melanoma segmentation, this article also adopts a U-shaped structural framework. However, since melanoma lesion areas vary in size and there are many lesions occlusions in the data set, in order to enable the segmentation model to adapt to the variability of lesions in the encoder stage, capture the local features of different regions, distinguish lesions and backgrounds, and improve segmentation To improve the accuracy, this paper uses a variety of feature fusion technologies, multi-scale feature extraction technology and attention mechanisms to design multi-scale coding block MSEB, channel-space attention skip connection CSSC and multi-scale decoding block MSDB respectively. Experimental comparisons were conducted with models such as DeepLabv3^[4], DenseASPP^[5], CA-Net^[6] and CE-Net^[7] on the ISIC2017 and ISIC2016 data sets. The results show that the model proposed in this article is superior to JA, ACC, DI is optimal in three important indicators. Afterwards, ablation experiments were conducted on the three modules proposed in this article on the above two data sets, and the results showed that there was a gain in improving the model effect.

Through this study, we hope to provide new ideas and methods for the further development of the field of melanoma segmentation and provide clinicians with more accurate and efficient melanoma diagnosis and treatment options. At the same time, we also hope to promote the widespread application of deep learning technology in the field of medical imaging and bring new breakthroughs and advances in medical diagnosis and treatment.

Related Works

On the problem of melanoma segmentation, melanomas usually have specific color characteristics, such as dark, irregular hues. Therefore, the early clinically used CAD (Computer Aided Diagnosis) system used color segmentation technology to convert the image into a specific color space, and then used threshold or clustering methods to segment the melanoma area^[8]. In addition to this, melanomas often have special textural features such as irregular shapes and edges. Therefore, some CAD uses technologies such as Gabor filter^[9] to extract texture information to achieve melanoma segmentation. The effectiveness of these methods also depends largely on the level of manual design^[10]. To this end, many researchers have carried out some work in recent years using melanoma segmentation methods based on deep learning. The Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) proposed by Yuan et al^[11] uses enhanced convolution and transposed convolution network for model training to accurately segment skin lesion areas. Based on U-Net, Chen et al^[12] proposed a multi-stage MS-UNet model with deep supervised learning strategy to improve the segmentation accuracy of skin lesions. In order to better represent the feature map, the Attention-UNet proposed by Rehman et al^[13] uses

the FocalLoss loss function to optimize the network training process. At the same time, the attention gate mechanism (Attention Gates, AG) is designed to fuse the deep feature map. Rich spatial information. Teodoro et al^[14] proposed a skin disease segmentation network based on Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). They used long-distance connections to capture global features, short-distance connections to capture local features, and introduced multi-scale loss functions. to optimize network training. In addition, the model designed by Islam et al^[15] integrates skip connection, atrous convolution and pyramid pooling modules to accurately segment skin lesion areas. He et al^[16] proposed an Adaptive Dual Attention Module (ADAM) network model for automatic skin lesion segmentation, in which one branch of the dual attention module aims to capture the boundary continuity of skin lesions through global average pooling, and the other branch aims to handle the irregularity of shape through context association.

Model Construction

As shown in Figure 1, the model proposed in this article adopts a U-shaped architecture and does the following work:

Fig. 1: MSCS-Unet architecture diagram

(1) The encoder part adopts modular MSEB structure which is stacked layer by layer. The module structure uses an Inception-like structure and uses four branches to replace the original 3×3 convolution. These four information paths are: 1×1 convolution in cascade form, 5×5 convolution, and 1×1 convolution. product, cascaded form of 1×1 convolution and 3×3 convolution, and cascaded form of 3×3 max pooling and 1×1 convolution. The output results of the four branches are spliced together to obtain the output result. This allows the encoder part of the model to better complete multi-channel information fusion.

(2) The CSSC method is designed to build the information path between the encoder and the decoder. Compared with the Skip Connection of the original Unet, the method proposed in this paper applies the channel attention mechanism and the spatial attention mechanism to the skip connection, which can effectively compensate for the effects of downsampling. The loss of spatial information enhances the global dimensional interaction ability of multi-scale features in each layer of the decoder.

(3) In order to obtain better image segmentation performance, this paper introduces multi-scale feature fusion in the decoding part. The deconvolution operation is completed through three different scale convolution kernels of 5×5 , 3×3 , and 1×1 set in the MSDB module, and then the three results are aggregated together to obtain the output of each MSDB. Through multi-scale decoding, the model can make full use of receptive fields of different scales, which is conducive to a more complete recovery of the feature information extracted in the encoding stage.

Because melanoma lesions vary widely in size, using a single scale may result in insufficient response to lesions of certain sizes. Moreover, the dermoscopic data set used has many problems such as lesion occlusion, which can easily cause interference to segmentation. Therefore, it is necessary to use multi-scale encoding methods to adapt the model

to the variability of lesions, capture local features in different areas, and better distinguish lesions from background to improve segmentation accuracy. If the outputs of convolution kernels of different sizes are spliced to complete multi-scale feature fusion, it will bring the cost of increasing the number of parameters. Based on the design ideas of GoogLeNet^[17], this paper designs an inception-like structure and integrates it into the convolution block in the Encoder part of U-Net. Its structure is shown in the Figure 2. This structure uses the dimensionality reduction operation of 1×1 convolution to realize information interaction between channels. In addition, each branch uses convolution kernels of different sizes to obtain information in different scales, which expands the receptive field of the Encoder's partial convolution operation. Then, richer semantic information is extracted and multi-scale coding is achieved.

Fig. 2: MSEB structure diagram

In the structure of U-Net, Skip-Connection is used as an information channel to connect the encoder and decoder, which is helpful to prevent information loss in the deep network. The lower levels of the fusion encoder contain more local and detailed information and The higher levels in the decoder contain more global and semantic information, helping to generate more semantic segmentation results. However, if you only build the encoder and decoder between the same layers, it will inevitably bring about some problems: if the number of network layers is too deep, the gap in feature information at both ends of the jump connection will be very large, resulting in poor information fusion effect. If the connection is only established between the encoder and decoder of the corresponding layer, it will cause a waste of feature information output by the encoding part of other layers, and the model's ability to capture contextual features needs to be improved. This paper applies the channel attention mechanism and spatial attention mechanism to skip connections and proposes channel-spatial attention skip connection CSASP. This module can effectively compensate for the loss of spatial information caused by downsampling and enhance the global dimensional interaction of multi-scale features in each layer of the decoder. As shown in Figure3, the input feature maps $x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times w \times c}$, F_1, F_2, F_3 represent the intermediate state and x_3 represent the output, then the input feature map goes through the following steps:

$$F_1 = \text{Concat}(x_1, x_2) \tag{3.1}$$

$$F_2 = \text{Sigmoid}(FC(\text{ReLu}(FC(F_1)))) \otimes F_1 \tag{3.2}$$

$$F_3 = \text{Sigmoid}(\text{Conv}(\text{ReLu}(\text{BN}(\text{Conv}(F_2)))))) \otimes F_2 \tag{3.3}$$

$$x_3 = FC(F_3) \tag{3.4}$$

Where $\otimes$ represents element-wise multiplication.

Fig. 3: CSSC structure diagram

Image features of different sizes of receptive fields can be better collected through multi-scale feature fusion. This article introduces multi-scale feature fusion to the decoder part of U-Net to improve the image segmentation effect. The decoding operation in U-Net includes: upsampling convolutional layer, input feature information obtained through skip connection and 3×3 deconvolution. As can be seen from the diagram, the multi-scale decoding structure proposed in this article is based on deconvolution and adds 1×1 deconvolution and 5×5 deconvolution in series. Through the 1×1 deconvolution operation, while ensuring that the feature information remains unchanged, the nonlinear features are greatly enhanced, helping the network to obtain better segmentation performance.

Fig .4: MSDB structure diagram

Experimental analysis

ISIC (International Skin Imaging Collaboration) is an international organization sponsored by the International Society for Digital Imaging of Skin and aims to improve the task of melanin diagnosis. This article uses the ISIC-2017^[18] data set and the ISIC-2016^[19] data set to conduct experiments to prove the effectiveness of the method. Because there are many hair occlusions, precipitated pigments, etc. that block the lesion area in this data set, as well as the blurring of the boundary of the lesion area, it poses a challenge. Therefore, it is difficult to complete accurate and clear image segmentation on this data set.

The ISIC2016 data set contains a total of 1279 skin lesion images in RGB format and pixel-level annotated images accurately annotated by experts, of which 900 images are used for training and 379 images are used for testing.

The ISIC-2017 data set has a total of 2000 training set images, 150 verification set images and 600 test set images, all of which are in RGB format. In the experiment, the data set was randomly divided according to the ratio of training set: validation set: test set = 7:1:2.

Since the image sizes in the ISIC2017 data set are not uniform, which will affect the training efficiency of the model, the data set images are adjusted uniformly. After statistically determining that the average aspect ratio of all images in the ISIC2017 data set is approximately 5:7, and after conducting multiple experiments, it was determined to adjust the size of all images to 224×160. In addition, due to the limited number of images in the ISIC2017 data set, which easily affects the training effect, this article uses data enhancement methods such as Gaussian blur processing, random rotation, and adding Gaussian noise to expand the data set.

The GPU model used in the experiment is NVIDIA Tesla V-100, the programming language is Python3.9, and the network model is built under the Pytorch framework.

After training, the optimal training parameters are obtained: batch-size is set to 10, epoch is set to 200, and the Adam optimizer is used as the optimizer during the training process. In order to prevent instability caused by too large a learning rate in the later stages of training, and too small a learning rate that will affect learning efficiency, this article uses the annealing strategy^[20] to set the learning rate. The formula is shown (4.4). This article sets the initial learning rate lr_{begin} to 0.001 and the number of training times to 200.

$$lr = \frac{1}{2}lr_{begin}(1 + \cos(\frac{T_{now}}{T_{total}}\pi)) \tag{4.1}$$

In order to examine the performance of the model more clearly and comprehensively, this article selected five indicators: Accuracy (AC), Sensitivity (SE), and Specificity (SP)、Jaccard index^[21](JA)、Dice coefficient^[22](DI) to measure the effectiveness of the model. Its expression is as follows:

$$AC = \frac{TN+TP}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \times 100\% \tag{4.2}$$

$$SP = \frac{TN}{FP+TN} \times 100 \tag{4.3}$$

$$SE = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \times 100\% \tag{4.4}$$

$$JA = \frac{TP}{TP+FN+FP} \times 100\% \tag{4.5}$$

$$DI = \frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP + FN + FP} \times 100\% \tag{4.6}$$

Among them, TP represents the number of true positive samples, FN represents the number of false negative samples, TN represents the number of true negative samples, and FP represents the number of false positive samples.

Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 show the performance of the model proposed in this article and several models that have achieved excellent performance in the field of image segmentation on the ISIC2017 and ISIC2016 data sets.

Model	SP/%	ACC/%	SE/%	JA/%	DI/%	Params
U-Net	97.15	95.28	91.09	85.30	92.93	33.0M
DeepLabv3	96.98	95.59	91.88	85.82	93.01	39.9M

DenseASPP	96.56	95.44	92.31	85.66	91.98	33.6M
CA-Net	97.09	95.60	91.75	86.03	92.36	2.8M
CE-Net	98.01	95.87	92.34	86.62	92.88	29.0M
Ours	98.05	96.64	92.77	88.41	93.87	15.4M

Table 4.1 Comparison of segmentation results of different models on the ISIC2016 data set

Table 4.2 Comparison of segmentation results of different models on the ISIC2017 data set

Model	SP/%	ACC/%	SE/%	JA/%	DI/%	Params
U-Net	97.28	94.01	80.49	72.19	84.19	33.0M
DeepLabv3	98.09	95.18	85.62	77.68	85.71	39.9M
DenseASPP	98.20	95.02	83.68	75.78	85.70	33.6M
CA-Net	98.26	94.96	82.89	76.28	84.64	2.8M
CE-Net	97.88	93.87	83.64	77.41	85.07	29.0M
Ours	98.30	95.59	83.22	78.26	86.37	15.4M

According to the above experimental results, it can be seen that the model proposed in this article is optimal in three important indicators: JA, ACC, and DI. On the ISIC2016 data set, these three indicators are 1.82%, 2.01%, 0.47% and 1.12%, 0.67%, 0.25% ahead of the original U-Net and the suboptimal model respectively. On the ISIC2017 data set, the model proposed in this article leads the U-Net model by 4.20%, 1.69%, and 1.55% in JA, ACC, and DI. It can be seen from these experimental data that the introduction of multiple feature fusion strategies in the decoder and encoder as well as the new skip connection that enhances the information flow between the encoder and the decoder proposed in this paper have played an important role, making the model more lightweight. It achieves an excellent balance between magnitude and efficient and accurate segmentation.

In order to further verify the effectiveness of the method used, this article uses U-Net as the Baseline and uses the ISIC2017 and ISIC2016 data sets to conduct ablation experiments. It can be seen from Table 4.3 and Table 4.4 that the segmentation results of the module proposed in this article are better than Baseline when used alone, indicating that the introduction of multiple feature fusion strategies in the decoder and encoder and the enhancement of the encoder and decoder proposed in this article The new skip connection for information flow is indeed a key element to improve model performance.

Conclusion

The shortcomings of the original U-Net in image segmentation mainly lie in the loss of semantic information and insufficient utilization. In order to solve this problem, this paper proposes the MSCS-Unet model based on the design idea of multi-scale feature fusion. This model introduces an inception-like structure in the encoder stage to obtain more semantic information. In the decoder stage, multi-scale processing of the deconvolution block helps the decoder to better restore the segmented image. In addition, in order to obtain more semantic information, based on the working principles of the spatial attention mechanism and the channel attention mechanism, a new skip connection method that can connect the encoding end and the decoding end is designed. Experiments show that the MSCS-Unet model has significant

performance compared with other medical image segmentation networks on the melanoma segmentation task. Finally, ablation experiments were conducted on the three modules highlighted in this model, and the results showed that each module has a positive effect on improving the performance of the model.

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